

Conscientia hypotheses - potential supplements to cell theory

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For reasons that remain unclear, despite roughly 4 billion years of cellular evolution, cell theory has only three well-accepted postulates¹. I previously proposed the gasocrine, circumiacentium, and informatio hypotheses, which state that all cells require gasocrine signaling², are limited by their environment³, and pass information⁴, respectively. Based on the gasocrine hypothesis, I proposed that a living cell is one that is capable of performing gasocrine processes⁵ and that consciousness potentially arises from the sum of gasocrine signaling activities². However, why must the criteria for a living cell be based only on gasocrine processes and not on other processes? And why would consciousness depend only on gasocrine signaling activities and not on all the "endogenous" and "environmental" molecule- or factor-based signaling in a cell or organism? Furthermore, how could multicellularity have arisen during evolution if unicellular organisms were not conscious of themselves or their environments? Therefore, I propose that cellular consciousness is the sum of its endogenous and environmental signaling, or, more simply, "cellular consciousness is the sum of its signaling activities." A corollary of this hypothesis is that "all cells require consciousness." These hypotheses can be falsified by finding a cell that exhibits consciousness when all its signaling is inhibited, as well as a cell that does not require consciousness. Thus, these hypotheses are potential supplements to cell theory.

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